

APECS Strategic Plan

2026
2030

This document describes the mission and strategic objectives of the **Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)** for 2026 to 2030, important preparation years for the 5th International Polar Year in 2032-2033.

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Version

This is **version 1.0** of the APECS Strategic Plan 2026-2030 - approved by the APECS Council on 8 June 2026 and published on 10 June 2026.

Preface

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) is an international, non-profit organization dedicated to facilitating collaboration among polar early career individuals and supporting their development. While APECS emerged from an engaged core of members in academia, we have evolved into a truly cross-sector and transdisciplinary organization—an aspect that we celebrate and actively seek to enhance. We recognize and welcome that the polar early career community includes individuals who may not identify as researchers, and we embrace diverse perspectives that strengthen our work.

Rapid climate change is transforming the polar regions at an unprecedented pace, underscoring the critical importance of polar research and the voices contributing to it. Critical to polar research is the meaningful inclusion of Indigenous Peoples and local communities who are both impacted by and integral to polar research. Their knowledge and perspectives are essential to understanding the poles and serving as stewards of these regions.

APECS occupies a unique and vital position within the broader polar community. Many established organizations recognize the

importance of supporting upcoming generations and rely on APECS to engage these new community members—equipping emerging professionals with the skills, networks, and opportunities they need to lead future polar research, policy and education. We embrace this responsibility and rise to it through the support of our sponsors and countless volunteer hours of our member community.

This Strategic Plan outlines APECS' priorities and activities for 2026-2030. It provides a framework for long-term development while deliberately maintaining flexibility for implementation. Rather than prescribing all possible or necessary steps, the plan establishes clear directional goals, empowering APECS' leadership to adapt actions on shorter timescales as both the organization and the polar community evolve. We will use this plan to guide our actions during the crucial years leading up to the 5th International Polar Year in 2032-33, positioning our community to contribute meaningfully to this effort.

Mission

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) is an international and transdisciplinary organization for early career professionals with interests in polar regions and the wider cryosphere.

APECS aims to foster an international network of polar early career community members across disciplines and professions to facilitate multi-directional knowledge exchange and capacity building. It facilitates career development, provides support through training and resources, and serves as a platform that empowers and advocates for the polar early career community.

APECS recognizes the value and complementary nature of diverse perspectives and knowledge systems and is guided by the principles of inclusivity, respect, meaningful and equitable engagement, knowledge-based decision making, and reciprocal cooperation.

APECS advances the development of polar research by inspiring future polar researchers, strengthening emerging leaders, uplifting early career voices, and upholding responsible and ethical research practices.

About APECS

APECS started in 2006 as an initiative of the International Polar Year (IPY) 2007-2008, and has been identified by major IPY sponsors as one of the most important legacies from the IPY 2007-2008. Today, APECS is continuously growing and has over 6,000 members worldwide, covering the breadth of polar, alpine and cryosphere research disciplines and spanning a network of more than 30 National Committees.

Image 1: Participants of the Polar Early Career World Summit (PECWS) 2025

APECS' structure is centered around a Council that is composed of a mix of elected and nominated positions. The APECS Council includes leaders of Project Groups and representatives of our National Committees.

The Executive Committee is part of and leads the Council and governs APECS in collaboration with the APECS International Directorate. The APECS International Directorate coordinates and administers all APECS activities and is financed by a host institution or consortium. A number of dedicated partners and APECS alumni support APECS by serving in committees adjacent to the rest of the volunteer structure: the Advisory Committee, which advises APECS' leadership in significant decisions and strategic development, and the Internal Evaluation Committee, which can be called upon to resolve conflicts or complaints between APECS members.

The APECS Handbook outlines the structure of APECS and core roles and processes within the organization. It includes the APECS Code of Conduct that applies to all of our activities.

Figure 1: Overview of APECS' structure and committees

APECS' activities

With its current activities, APECS supports capacity building across the polar early career community with a focus on transdisciplinary, internationally coordinated and equitable polar research. APECS does this by:

- facilitating capacity building and career development,
- disseminating early career opportunities and resources,
- fostering community growth and connection,
- advocating for the inclusion of diverse perspectives of the early career community in research planning and policy making,
- promoting Open Science and developing research collaborations, and
- supporting education and outreach activities.

The involvement of the APECS International Directorate in externally funded projects complements member-driven, grassroots initiatives, resulting in a diverse portfolio of activities.

Image 2: APECS President 2023-2024, José Queirós, speaking during an APECS event at Arctic Science Summit Week 2024.

Learn more about APECS and join us!

Become an APECS member

Membership in APECS is free and open to everyone. Become a member now by registering at www.apecs.is and join an international community of polar early career professionals.

Join APECS' leadership

You can join APECS' leadership and help shape the future of polar research. Visit www.apecs.is to learn more about the different leadership roles and apply.

Collaborate with APECS

Please contact the APECS International Directorate at info@apecs.is to explore opportunities to collaborate.

Image 3: APECS Vice President 2023-2024, Lina Madaj, speaking during an APECS event at Arctic Science Summit Week 2024.

You can find more information at
www.apecs.is

APECS' strategy for 2026-2030

APECS' development for 2026-2030 will be based on three pillars: improving governance processes and structure, meaningfully engaging a diverse polar community, and implementing focus activities and priorities.

1 Improving governance processes and structure

Adapting governance and enhancing support structures

Securing organizational capacity

Cultivating meaningful community service roles and volunteer engagement

Monitoring activity and progress

2 Meaningfully engaging a diverse polar community

Increasing the accessibility and inclusivity of APECS

Sustaining and expanding APECS' partnerships

3 Implementing focus activities and priorities

Activities supporting community needs

Reviewing current activities

Preparing for the 5th International Polar Year (2032-33)

1

Improving governance processes and structure

APECS thrives through the active involvement of a broad membership base, guided by organizational structure and internal processes. Continued growth requires adapting APECS' governance structures to support effective operations. It is essential to balance the decision-making and implementation authority of groups in APECS' structure with the need for consistent coordination across the organization. These good governance practices provide the foundation for meaningful engagement and impactful work. During 2026-2030, APECS will strengthen multiple components of its internal procedures and structures.

Adapting governance and enhancing support structures

- **Dynamically review and update APECS' governance processes** to ensure decision-making, roles, and responsibilities remain clear, transparent, and responsive to evolving needs
- **Strengthen coordination across and support for National Committees**
 - **Revising membership administration** to streamline processes and improve accessibility
 - **Enabling the sharing of best practices** to foster learning and efficiency across committees
 - **Fostering collaboration** between committees and with the broader APECS network to strengthen engagement and impact
- **Improve onboarding processes** for new members and APECS' leadership roles to ensure clarity and inclusion
- **Document institutional knowledge** to preserve organizational memory and continuity
- **Provide clear guidance** in multiple formats and simplify processes where possible

Securing organizational capacity

- Pursue opportunities to establish **satellite offices of the APECS International Directorate** and seek to increase the capacity of the International Directorate to enhance support and diversify activities
- Seek additional **financial support** for activities that directly benefit the polar early career community and actively participate in applications for external funding through the APECS International Directorate
- Assess the **potential for APECS to become a financially freestanding organization** to aid long-term stability and sustainability
- **Prepare for an anticipated increase in activities** in relation to the 5th International Polar Year (IPY-5) in 2032-2033, and ensure that APECS can respond effectively to growing engagement and coordination demands
- **Strengthen internal capacity for sustainable growth and continuity** by developing long-term staffing, funding, and operational strategies that enable the organization to maintain consistent support for its members and partners

Cultivating meaningful community service roles and volunteer engagement

APECS aims to cultivate meaningful community service roles and deepen volunteer engagement by ensuring accessibility and inclusivity in its application processes and selection criteria. Current roles and tasks will be reviewed and, where needed, redesigned to reflect evolving priorities and equitable workloads. Member contributions will be honored through transparent communication of the benefits of involvement and the creation of opportunities for professional growth and visibility.

The International Directorate will investigate mechanisms for providing honoraria or other forms of compensation for specific tasks or projects to enhance engagement across the community, with particular attention to supporting equitable participation of underrepresented and insufficiently funded groups. APECS will continue to provide opportunities for members to take initiative, gain leadership experience, and contribute to the organization's mission in practical and impactful ways, fostering a sense of ownership and shared purpose across the community.

Monitoring activity and progress

An essential component of governance is monitoring progress, both quantitatively and qualitatively. APECS will create and implement simple but effective mechanisms to track activities across the organization and evaluate progress towards the strategic goals outlined in this document.

The APECS International Directorate will review and update internal reporting procedures by 2027 to reduce complexity while maintaining sufficient information availability.

2

Meaningfully engaging a diverse polar community

Increasing the accessibility and inclusivity of APECS

APECS strives to be an inclusive network, open to all polar early career professionals. Continuous evaluation and subsequent action are critical for further progress towards this goal. The implementation of this ambition will be based on multiple specific approaches.

- **Expanding membership and engagement by**
 - **identifying underrepresentation** across disciplines, regions, and identities; including setting measurable targets to track progress and improved participation
 - **increasing reach** through targeted outreach, collaboration with regional networks, and visibility at relevant events and on relevant platforms
 - **broadening recruitment** by developing inclusive strategies that attract members from diverse backgrounds, sectors and career stages
 - **encouraging continued participation** through recognition of service and provision of professional development opportunities within APECS activities and leadership roles
- **Lowering barriers to participation through**
 - **online** activities, **digital** modes of engagement and **multilingual** information
 - strategic planning of in-person activities and **prioritization of resources** for underrepresented groups
 - **flexible opportunities** that accommodate varying personal and professional commitments, responsibilities, and cultural contexts
 - **mentorship and peer support** programs to encourage active participation
- **Reviewing application processes and selection criteria for opportunities** to ensure transparency, inclusivity, and fairness. This includes simplifying procedures where possible, clearly communicating expectations, and minimizing barriers that may discourage applicants from underrepresented regions, disciplines, or backgrounds.
- **Embedding the values** of inclusivity, respect, meaningful and equitable engagement, knowledge-based decision making, and reciprocal cooperation into all APECS initiatives and creating space for culturally safe dialogue and knowledge exchange.
- Ensuring that the **APECS Code of Conduct** is effectively applied across the organization's activities and reporting mechanisms are accessible and efficient.
- Establishing clear avenues for the polar early career community to provide **input and feedback** to guide APECS' development.

Sustaining and expanding APECS' partnerships

APECS emphasizes the importance of strengthening its current collaborations while actively pursuing new opportunities with organizations, networks, and communities that share our mission and values. To ensure continuity and long-term impact, APECS aims to institutionalize partnerships through clear agreements, defined roles, and shared objectives.

APECS envisions sustained collaboration with the following types of organizations (exemplified by non-exclusive lists of partners):

- **Scientific institutions and polar infrastructure, logistics and data coordination bodies** (e.g., universities, *INTERACT*¹, *COMNAP*², *FARO*³, *SIOS*⁴) – collaborating on research projects, training initiatives, and knowledge exchange to strengthen scientific capacity
- **Research coordination, policy advisory, and non-profit organizations** (e.g., *SCAR*⁵, *IASC*⁶, *SOOS*⁷, *Antarctica InSync*, *Arctic Council Working Groups*, *ICIMOD*⁸, *IPCC*⁹, *WWF*¹⁰) – aligning (research) priorities, advancing capacity building, and fostering early career engagement in coordinated science efforts
- **Multilateral or intergovernmental cooperation frameworks** (e.g., *Arctic Council*, *Antarctic Treaty System*, *UNFCCC*¹¹, *Arctic Mayors' Forum*) – contributing early career perspectives and promoting youth voices in international polar governance and policy processes
- **Indigenous Peoples' organizations** (e.g., *Permanent Participants of the Arctic Council*) – strengthening dialogue, mutual learning, and collaboration with knowledge holders and rights-holders
- **Early career networks and youth organizations** (e.g., *PSECCO*¹², *AYN*¹³, *Ikaarvik*, *PYRN*¹⁴, *YESS*¹⁵) – exchanging best practices and building community across organizations
- **Funding bodies and grant agencies supporting polar research** – contributing to discussions on research priorities, equitable capacity building, and best practices for inclusive and responsible research
- **Polar organizations with a focus on public engagement or education** (e.g., *Students on Ice*) – co-developing accessible educational materials and co-organizing events to communicate polar research to broader audiences
- **Symposia and forum conveners** (e.g., *Arctic Frontiers*, *ArcticNet*) – facilitating participation of early career professionals in international polar dialogue and knowledge exchange events

Through strengthening these external relationships, APECS aims to consolidate its role in connecting its members and the broader polar community, ensuring that early career professionals have pathways to engage and opportunities to participate in polar research coordination.

¹ International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

² Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programs

³ Forum of Arctic Research Operators

⁴ Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System

⁵ Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research

⁶ International Arctic Science Committee

⁷ Southern Ocean Observing System

⁸ International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development

⁹ Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

¹⁰ World Wildlife Fund

¹¹ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

¹² Polar Science Early Career Community Office

¹³ Arctic Youth Network

¹⁴ Permafrost Young Researchers Network

¹⁵ Young Earth System Scientists

3

Implementing focus activities and priorities

Activities supporting community needs

This section outlines how APECS will translate its mission into tangible impact through targeted activities. Building on the insights gathered from its community and partners, APECS aims to foster a supportive, equitable, and interconnected polar early career community. From 2026–2030, APECS will strengthen its role as both an enabler and advocate—creating pathways for early career professionals to develop skills, shape research priorities, and contribute meaningfully to polar science and environmental stewardship.

APECS nurtures capacity building across the polar early career community and in the coming years will focus on:

- facilitating capacity building and career development,
- advocating for the inclusion of diverse perspectives of the early career community in research planning and policy making,
- disseminating opportunities and resources,
- championing belonging, accessibility, justice, equity, diversity and inclusion (BAJEDI),
- fostering relationship building and creating spaces for knowledge and experience sharing,
- enabling networking, peer support, and mentoring,
- improving research practices, promoting Open Science and developing research collaborations, and
- supporting education and outreach activities.

This list includes current activities that we will continue as well as recent and developing topics of interest.

In the context of the *Polar Early Career World Summit (PECWS) 2025*, APECS and its partners engaged 238 polar early career professionals from across the globe to shape collective priorities for the future of polar research. Moving forward, APECS will advocate for the inclusion of this community-driven vision into planning processes and activities, urging the polar research community to rethink systems, value relationships, and strengthen pathways for equitable participation. The *PECWS Synthesis Report*¹ identifies six cross-cutting topics which APECS will work to address from 2026-2030:

Community-centered research practices

Honoring multiple ways of knowing and doing

Ensuring safety and well-being

Open and accessible science

Funding system transformation

Effectively communicating science

¹ Dryák-Vallies, M. C., Strand, S. M., Payne, M. R., & Schlindwein, A. (2025). Polar Early Career World Summit Synthesis Report. Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) International Directorate and Polar Science Early Career Community Office (PSECCO). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994869>

Reviewing current activities

APECS will continuously review its current activities and initiatives to facilitate alignment with the 2026-2030 Strategic Plan and to ensure that the organization's limited capacity is used efficiently. This evaluation will identify where adjustments or new approaches are needed to maintain relevance, inclusivity, and impact. Member-driven initiatives will continue to be central to APECS' activities, complemented by targeted actions coordinated by APECS' leadership.

Activities will continuously be adjusted in response to evolving priorities, ensuring that APECS' programs remain dynamic and responsive to the needs of early career professionals and the polar research community.

Preparing for the 5th International Polar Year (2032-33)

APECS aspires to take a leading role in the planning and implementation of the 5th International Polar Year (2032–33). The 2026-2030 period will be used to strengthen organizational capacity, expand partnerships, and develop initiatives that ensure early career professionals are meaningfully involved in IPY-5 activities.

This includes supporting youth-led research and engagement, fostering international collaboration, and promoting equitable participation across regions and knowledge systems.

**International
Polar Year**
2032–2033

You can find more information at

www.ipy5.net

IPY-5 in 2032-33 aims to address urgent global challenges by advancing polar research, focusing on the impacts of climate change in the Arctic and Antarctic. This coordinated effort will bring together scientists, Indigenous knowledge holders, and global stakeholders to produce actionable insights for mitigating and adapting to environmental changes, while promoting international collaboration and inclusivity.

About this Strategic Plan

Contributions

The development of this Strategic Plan was led by a team of members of the Executive Committee and the International Directorate. It was reviewed by the Council and the Advisory Committee and includes input from the APECS membership and the wider polar early career community.

Adoption and citation

The final version was approved by the Council on 8 June 2026, published on 10 June 2026, and can be referenced through the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19161093.

Evaluation

A structured evaluation of the progress towards the aims described in this Strategic Plan should be conducted in 2028 to determine the need for revised action and inform the development of APECS' next Strategic Plan.

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